

**INTERNATIONAL EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN CHINA AS A FACTOR IN PREPARING
DESIGNER-EDUCATORS WITH EXPERIENCE IN INTERCULTURAL
COMMUNICATION**

Vitchynkina K. O.

lecturer

College of international education of Wuhan university of technology

c. Wuhan, PRC, e-mail: vikaltd@163.com

In response to the industry's need for a new generation of market-oriented, management-oriented, research-driven, and well-rounded designers in China, there is an urgent mission to reform modern design education based on multicultural principles.

The main trend in education development in China has been the reform of higher education based on multicultural principles. The National Commission of Education in China proposed the organization of Sino-foreign cooperation in education management. This has allowed for the usage of educational resources and teaching methods from leading universities worldwide and improve the content of education in national educational programs [1].

The Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Sino-Foreign Cooperation in School Management and the Content Evaluation of Sino-Foreign Joint Education is specified that the presence of foreign teachers is mandatory in international educational programs [2; 3]. This is also emphasized by Lu Inchun and experts from the Institute of Advanced Education Experience, noting that the proportion of foreign teachers instructing core courses should be no less than 25% [4], while the remaining portion consists of teachers who are Chinese citizens. Consequently, there are special requirements for Chinese teachers, who are expected to possess experience in intercultural communication.

A thorough analyze of scientific sources reveals that the investigated issue is extensively examined in the discourse. The discussions encompass various aspects,

such as the implementation of international educational programs (Zheng Lei, Tian Jin), the establishment of educational environments grounded in interculturality (Wang Xiao Jie, L. Zeegen, B. Canniffe, Pan Lu Sheng, T. Triggs), and the exploration of strategies for enhancing design education (E. Bazilyuk, V. Danilenko, V. Prusak, O. Fursa). However, in their research, researchers do not analyze the experience of international educational programs as a factor in preparing design educators with intercultural communication experience.

The article examines international educational programs in China's higher education institutions as a factor in preparing designer-educators with intercultural communication experience.

For example, in the international educational-professional program for training future graphic design professionals at Wuhan University of Technology and Trinity Saint David University, teaching is conducted jointly by Chinese and foreign educators, using bilingual instruction in English and Chinese. This aims to cultivate international communication and design experience, along with fundamental knowledge, theoretical understanding, and creative abilities which are necessary for artistic creation, as it outlined in the Application Guide for the Sino-British Bachelor of Arts program at Wuhan University of Technology [5].

Graduates of international educational programs in China, such as the program at Wuhan University of Technology and Trinity Saint David University, have the unique opportunity to become lecturers in these programs. Thus, international programs serve as the foundation for preparing not only designers with intercultural communication experience but also educators capable of teaching design according to the educational standards of other countries and possessing intercultural communication experience.

Graduates of international educational programs in China possess a profound understanding of the culture, mindset, and intricacies of the Chinese higher education system. This makes them valuable educators in these programs. The bilingual environment in which graduates are immersed during their studies in international programs makes them effective communicators with both Chinese students and

colleagues from other countries. Graduates of international educational programs have experience in intercultural communication, which enables them to adapt easily to working in an international environment and implement educational programs developed according to the standards of other countries. Their competence in the field of design, acquired through international educational programs, makes them experts in their field, capable of imparting their knowledge and skills to future graphic designers.

Graduates of international educational programs in China have the opportunity to implement innovative teaching methods they have learned during their studies in international programs and contribute to the development of design education in China. These graduates open up global perspectives for Chinese students, helping them gain international experience and broaden their horizons in the field of graphic design.

Intercultural communication is an important pedagogical factor in preparing future design instructors for international programs in the People's Republic of China. This aspect of teaching contributes to the development of students' international cultural competence, broadens their perspectives, and deepens their understanding of different cultures.

Several key aspects can be considered when implementing intercultural communication in the preparation of future graphic design professionals who, after passing professional exams and obtaining a professional teaching certificate, can teach design in international programs in China:

1. Intercultural competence: Ensuring the development of students' intercultural competence, which includes understanding and respecting different cultures, mindsets, and values. This can be achieved through teaching intercultural skills, exploring intercultural communication strategies, and fostering effective interactions with individuals from diverse cultures.

2. Language proficiency: Developing students' language skills, especially in English, which is the international language of communication in the field of design. Language proficiency helps students effectively communicate in future with

designers and customers different countries and convey their ideas and concepts in an international context.

3. Intercultural projects and internships: Organizing intercultural projects, collaborative internships, and exchanges with other universities and organizations abroad. This allows students to familiarize themselves with other cultures, gain practical experience working in an international environment, and deepen their knowledge of global trends in the field of design.

4. Intercultural learning materials: Usage intercultural learning materials, examples, and projects that encourage students to consider design from different cultural perspectives. This helps broaden their horizons and fosters creative activity and innovative approaches to design.

5. Intercultural community: Creating an intercultural community of students and teachers where they can exchange thoughts, ideas, and experiences, collaborate on tasks, and create new projects together. This fosters mutual understanding, mutual support, and the creation of a conducive environment for intercultural communication.

International educational programs play a significant role in preparing designer-educators with experience in intercultural communication. Here are a few theses that reflect this factor:

1. Exposure to diverse cultural perspectives: International programs provide students with exposure to a wide range of cultural perspectives, fostering their understanding and appreciation of different cultural contexts. This exposure enhances their ability to navigate intercultural interactions effectively.

2. Multicultural classroom environment: International programs often attract students and educators from various cultural backgrounds, creating a multicultural classroom environment. This setting encourages students to engage in cross-cultural dialogue, share experiences, and learn diverse perspectives.

3. Intercultural teaching methodologies: International programs emphasize the integration of intercultural teaching methodologies, incorporating diverse instructional approaches and strategies. These methods encourage students to explore

and appreciate different cultural influences in their design education.

In conclusion, it can be stated that international educational programs for preparing future professionals in graphic design in the PRC play a crucial role in shaping competitive experts and design instructors with a high level of intercultural communication. These programs provide students with opportunities to broaden their perspectives, deepen their understanding of different cultural contexts, and develop communication skills. Acquiring experience in international collaboration, language proficiency, and participation in cultural exchanges contributes to the development of graduates who are competitive in the job market and capable of effectively teaching design while considering intercultural aspects. Therefore, international educational programs in the PRC have a positive impact on the preparation of future professionals and design educators, providing them with valuable intercultural communication skills and making them competitive in the global job market. Further in-depth research is needed to analyze the characteristics of educational and methodological support of international educational programs in higher education institutions in the PRC.

References

1. Вітчизніна К. Порівняння міжнародних та національних програм освіти майбутніх фахівців із графічного дизайну в зво кнр. *Духовно- інтелектуальне виховання і навчання молоді в XXI столітті* : міжнар. період. зб. наук. пр., м. Харків. Харків, 2022. С. 772–774.

2. 中华人民共和国中外合作办学条例(Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Chinese-Foreign Cooperation in Running Schools): 中华人民共和国国务院令(State Council of the People's Republic of China.) from 01.09.2003 y. 372 号 (№ 372) .

3. 中外合作办学评估内容(Evaluation content of Chinese-foreign cooperative education). 教育部教育涉外监管信息网(Ministry of Education Education Foreign-related Supervision Information Network)北京 (Beijing)

4. 吕迎春(Lu Yingchun). 低分高就看清中外合作办学的真面目(Lows core sand highs cores show the true face of Chinese-foreign cooperative education). 卓越教育考试研究院 (*Excellence in Education Examination Institute*). URL: <https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s?biz=MjM5NDgyMTg1Ng==&mid=2656665704&idx=1&sn=f8784f98ea763055d1d35153632aed6a&chksm=bd2cc3e78a5b4af15d451b741e3333326037237c68ac56aedf3c9c989ad73a1f6a31d1e0cc85&scene=27> (accessed: 14.05.2023)

5. 武汉理工大学中英艺术本科项目 2022 年报考指南(Guide to applying for the Sino-British bachelor of Arts Program at Wuhan University of technology 2022). 武汉理工大学 (*Wuhan University of technology*). 2022-05-17 URL: http://www.whut.edu.cn/gjyy/zwhzbx/bxzk/202205/t20220517_528569.htm. (accessed: 14.05.2023)